

ABSTRACT

Modeling the pHLA/TCR Complex in a Lipid Bilayer Environment

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Multiple sclerosis (MS) is mediated by T cell responses to antigens of the central nervous system, such as myelin basic protein (MBP). The Human Leucocyte Antigen (HLA) locus is the main region associated with the disease, where certain alleles of the DRB1 gene have been linked to both predisposition and protection against MS. The binding groove of the HLA-DR heterodimer interacts with specific peptides, while T-cell receptor (TCR) recognize the complex formed by the peptide and HLA (pHLA). Understanding the preferences of this interaction may help understand susceptibility to MS. Although X-ray crystallography has been employed to determine the structure of pHLA/TCR, it does not encompass the transmembrane regions. Therefore, the aim of this study was to model the pHLA/TCR complex within a membrane environment to evaluate its stability and dynamic behavior. The complete model of this complex was generated using the MODELLER program. Atomic coordinates from the pHLA/TCR crystal (PDB ID: 1YMM) were extracted and used as the initial model, with structural gaps filled using models available in the AlphaFold Protein Structure Database. A loop refinement algorithm was employed to adjust the positions of the binding, transmembrane, and cytoplasmic regions, which were oriented along the z-axis, while geometric constraints were imposed to preserve the integrity of the transmembrane helices. A heterogeneous lipid bilayer was constructed via the CHARMM-GUI server, and subsequently, the modeled complex was manually inserted into two lipid bilayers using VMD software. A 50 ns molecular dynamics (MD) simulation was conducted using the GROMACS program. The best model resulting of pHLA/TCR exhibited helices aligned parallel to the z-axis, enabling their insertion into lipid bilayers, followed by MD simulations. The resulting trajectories demonstrated that the system achieved stability throughout the simulated period, maintaining the complete integrity of the pHLA-TCR interaction. This suggests that the model is suitable for further investigations into this complex interaction in membranous environments. To analyze the potential influence of DRB1 gene polymorphisms on MS susceptibility, the next steps of this research involve modeling pHLA-DR complexes corresponding to different alleles and comparing their interactions with specific TCRs and peptides.

Keywords: pHLA/TCR Interaction; Polymorphisms; Structural Bioinformatics.

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